

THE INFLUENCE OF THE LITHOLOGICAL-TECTONIC FACTOR ON THE EROSION-DRAINAGE NETWORK IN THE CATCHMENT OF THE BYUYUKDERE RIVER (THE EASTERN RHODOPE)

Miloslava Stefanova, Valentina Nikolova, Ivan Dimitrov

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: m.sstefanova@mgu.bg, v.nikolova@mgu.bg, ivan.d.ivanov@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The interaction between the lithology, the strike and dip of geological layers, and the tectonic factor influences erosion processes and the development of river systems. Understanding these interactions is essential for territorial planning, implementing erosion control measures, and ensuring effective environmental management. In this consideration, the current study aims to determine the presence or absence of a relationship between lithological-tectonic features and the erosion-drainage network in the Byuyukdere River watershed. The studied watershed is located in the Northeastern Rhodopes Depression (southern Bulgaria) and is characterised by active erosion processes. The analysis was conducted in the ArcGIS Pro environment (ESRI Inc.), using a geological map at a scale of 1:50,000 and a digital elevation model with a resolution of 12.5 meters (ALOS PALSAR). The stream orientation was analysed, considering the lithological composition, bedding surfaces, and fault tectonics. The results show that in the scope of the studied watershed the erosion-drainage network is mainly controlled by lithological variations and less by tectonics.

Key words: water erosion, geology, gullies, river system.

ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ЛИТОЛОГО-ТЕКТОНСКИЯ ФАКТОР ВЪРХУ ЕРОЗИОННО ДРЕНАЖНАТА МРЕЖА ВЪВ ВОДОСБОРА НА РЕКА БЮЮКДЕРЕ (ИЗТОЧНИ РОДОПИ)

Милослава Стефанова, Валентина Николова, Иван Димитров
Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. Взаимодействието между литологията, посоката и наклона на геоложките пластове и тектонския фактор оказва влияние върху ерозионните процеси и развитието на речните системи. Разбирането на тези взаимодействия е от съществено значение за териториалното планиране, прилагането на мерки за контрол на ерозията и ефективно управление на околната среда. Във връзка с това, целта на настоящото изследване е да се установи наличие или отсъствие на връзка между литолого-тектонски особености и ерозионно дренажната мрежа във водосбора на река Бююкдере. Изследваният водосбор е част от Североизточнородопското понижение и се характеризира с активна проява на ерозионни процеси. Анализът е направен в ArcGIS Pro среда (ESRI Inc.) на базата на геоложка карта в мащаб 1: 50 000 и цифров модел на релефа с резолюция 12.5 метра (ALOS PALSAR). Анализирани са ориентацията на ерозионно-дренажната мрежа предвид литоложкия състав, ориентировката на пластове и разломната тектоника. Резултатите от анализа показват, че в изследвания водосбор ерозионно-дренажната мрежа се контролира главно от литоложкото разнообразие и по-малко от тектониката.

Ключови думи: водна ерозия, геология, ровини, речна система.

Introduction

The interaction between lithology and tectonic processes plays a critical role in shaping landscapes and controlling erosion rates. In tectonically stable regions, lithological variability — particularly differences in rock strength and weathering resistance — directly governs erosion rates and drainage development. Different types of lithology lead to varying erosion rates, which alter landscapes over the course of time (Haag et al., 2025). Softer, less resistant lithology, such as unconsolidated sediments or weakly cemented rocks, is subject to rapid weathering and erosion, often resulting in densely developed and highly dissected drainage networks. In contrast, more resistant rocks, such as quartzites or volcanics, typically form flatted topographies with sparse drainage due to their greater resistance to weathering and lower erodibility. The absence of stabilising vegetation, combined with the presence of easily erodible materials, promotes the formation of extensive erosion-drainage networks. In tectonically active regions, the relationship between lithology and erosion is modified and often intensified by structural influences. As McCarthy et al. (2019) point out, in areas with recent tectonic activity, both the type of rock and tectonic features have a big impact on how fast the land erodes and changes — sometimes even more than the climate. Tectonic structures, such as folds and faults, impose directional constraints and introduce mechanical weaknesses

that significantly influence drainage patterns. Studies have demonstrated that the rate of surface runoff and the density of the drainage network vary within fold structures, with higher river network density indicating more intense erosional activity. (Delcaillau et al., 2006; Ramsey et al., 2008). Fault systems, as long-term expressions of regional tectonic regimes, form structural boundaries that strongly influence the orientation, evolution, and incision depth of fluvial systems. Active fault zones commonly act as preferential erosion corridors due to enhanced rock fracturing and localised mechanical breakdown, facilitating focused surface water flow and the development of fault-aligned valleys (Schumm, 1986; Twidale, 2004). The alignment of high-order drainage segments along major faults often reflects this tectonic control, while lower-order tributaries may develop independently, responding more strongly to local lithology or slope conditions. Furthermore, the coupling of lithology and tectonics plays a central role in long-term landscape evolution. Tectonic uplift alters local base levels and slope gradients, triggering differential erosion that is strongly modulated by lithological heterogeneity. Yanites et al. (2017) emphasise that variations in erosion rates and landscapes are best understood through an integrated approach, where geological composition interacts with tectonic forcing to determine drainage structure, relief evolution, and landscape dynamics.

A synthesis of recent studies (Gabet, 2019; Bartley et al.,

2020; Beeson & McCoy, 2020; Seagren & Schoenbohm, 2021; Haag et al., 2025) demonstrates that lithological and tectonic factors are primary controls on drainage network development, erosion intensity, and fluvial morphology. On the other hand, the drainage network is one of the most dynamic components of the landscape, continuously responding to geological and geomorphological processes. In this context, watershed morphometric parameters, such as drainage density, bifurcation ratio, and stream order, serve as effective indicators of underlying structural and lithological influences. The interaction between lithology, tectonic activity, and the orientation of geological strata not only influences erosion patterns but also governs the evolution, adjustment, and hierarchical organisation of river systems. This relationship is especially prominent in small to medium-sized drainage basins (generally under 1000 km²), where local geological and climate conditions have a more direct influence on fluvial dynamics. Analysing the morphometric characteristics of drainage networks within the framework of regional litho-structural settings provides valuable insights into basin development trends. Such understanding is essential for quantifying erosion potential and for developing land management strategies aimed at mitigating hydro-geomorphological hazards.

Regarding the above, the aim of the current study is to assess how the lithological-tectonic features influence the development of the erosion-drainage network in the catchment of the Byuyukdere River. The results of the study can be used as indicators for the assessment of the erosion processes in the watershed scale.

Data and methods

The area of interest in this study is the Byuyukdere River watershed. It is located in the Eastern Rhodope Mountains in southern Bulgaria, and forms part of the larger hydrological basin of the Arda River (Fig. 1). The total surface area of the Byuyukdere watershed is approximately 27 km². The river itself originates in the vicinity of the village of Yavorovo, located in the northern section of the watershed, and flows predominantly southwards until it discharges into the Kardzhali Dam.

The watershed exhibits a diverse topography characterised by varying slope gradients, which play a critical role in shaping hydrological behaviour, surface runoff dynamics, erosion intensity, and the development of the drainage network. Areas with slopes of up to 3° are limited in extent, covering only about 2% of the total watershed area (Fig. 2). These relatively flat zones typically exhibit low surface runoff and minimal erosion activity. In contrast, moderate slopes ranging between 3° and 15° dominate the central part of the watershed. This slope interval takes around 44% of the Byuyukdere River catchment. This terrain represents a transitional zone from lowlands to more rugged uplands and is typified by increased erosional processes. These conditions foster the development of a dense fluvial network, including numerous small tributaries and intermittent streams that contribute to the overall hydrological complexity of the basin.

Fig. 1. Study area

Fig. 2. Slope map

The majority of the watershed — approximately 47% — comprises areas with steeper inclines, ranging from 15° to 30°. These slopes are highly susceptible to intensive surface erosion, which significantly affects soil stability and sediment transport. The most pronounced topographic gradients,

exceeding 30°, are found in about 7% of the watershed. These steepest areas are concentrated primarily in the lower reaches of the river, close to its confluence with the Kardzhali Dam. Their steepness is largely a result of tectonic activity and faulting within the river valley, combined with ongoing erosion processes.

Additionally, steep slopes are also a distinguishing feature of certain headwater valleys formed by first- and second-order streams, particularly in the eastern and northern sectors of the watershed. These streams, classified according to the Strahler stream order system (Strahler, 1957), contribute to the complex geomorphological and hydrological structure of the basin.

Geologically, the area belongs to the Northeastern Rhodopes Depression. The lithological composition is predominantly represented by volcanogenic-sedimentary rocks, including tuffs, tuffites, and breccia-conglomerates. Additionally, andesites and latites are present, along with more limited areas containing limestones and marls (Fig. 3). The lithological composition of the watershed combined with the hydro-climatic conditions determine to a great extent the formation of Chromic Cambisol and Chromic Luvisol (FAO-UNESCO-ISRIC, 1990) which are moderate to highly susceptible to erosion. On the other hand, the outcrop of the different petrographic composition affects the selective erosion. All these features influence the pattern of the drainage network of the area.

The current study is based on a geological map at the scale of 1:50 000, map sheet K-35-75-G (Yordanov et al., 2008), a digital elevation model (DEM) with 12.5 m horizontal resolution, and field observations. Based on the DEM, the stream lines were generated within ArcGIS Pro, 3.4.0 (ESRI Inc., 2024) environment. Their order was determined using the Strahler method (Strahler, 1957). The pattern of the erosional-drainage network was analysed in consideration of the lithological and tectonic features of the studied watershed. For the purpose of the study, the Byuyukdere catchment was divided into 4 domains (Fig. 3). All identified permanent and temporary streams were considered in the analysis. Rose-diagrams of the direction of the streams in each one of the domains were created and compared to the fault tectonics and bedding.

Analysis of structural and petrographic controls on erosion and drainage network orientation

In terms of geotectonics, the watershed of the river Byuyukdere is located in a regional tectonic fold known as the Mastatepe syncline. It comprises Oligocene pyroclastic and mixed sedimentary-pyroclastic rocks in the cores, and Eocene volcano-sedimentary units in the limbs. This syncline has been complicated by tectonic faults with two main orientations, N-NW and W-NW. The NE and E-W fault directions are present to a lesser extent. The major N-NW and W-NW faults have proven normal fault displacement, indicated by the age of the sediments they displace. They have less obvious strike-slip displacement, which is inferred by the lozenge shape of the basins they delineate. These basins have the geometry of pull-apart basins.

The upper Eocene horst structure to east of the Byuyukdere and to south of the hinge of the Mastatepe syncline (southern limb of the syncline) is particularly well defined. It is infilled with Priabonian conglomerates and sandstones with abundant evidence for syntectonic exotic blocks – olistostromes, indicating that the fault boundary was active during the Priabonian sediment deposition.

1 - fine-ash and vitriclastic acidic tuffs, calcareous tuffites, and platy impure limestones; 2 – andesites; 3 – latites to andesites; 4 - coarse-ash intermediate-acid tuffs, tuffites, and epiclastics; 5 - latitic to andesitic lava breccias; 6 - organogenic limestones; 7 - sandstones with rarely developed breccia-conglomerate beds; 8 - flysch; 9 - alternation of marls, siltstones, sandstones, tuffs, and tuffites; 10 - polyclastic conglomerate-breccias; 11- fault; 12 – normal fault; 13 - Inclined bedding; In red colour: 1; 2; 3; 4 – number of the domains; red lines – domain's borders

Fig. 3. Geological map (after Yordanov et al., 2008 with amendments)

The N-NW bounding fault that delimits the Priabonian from the west, along which the river Byuyukdere flows, also exposes features of a synsedimentary tectonic activity. The Byuyukdere river follows this N-NW striking fault for about 2.5 km, as upper Eocene sediments are exposed from the east of the river valley, and lower Oligocene lava flows and subvolcanic rock of intermediate composition are exposed to the west of the river valley. Based on this observation, it can be concluded that the larger faults of above-mentioned directions were active at least during the Upper Eocene and controlled the subsidence and uplift of the tectonic blocks.

On the geological map of Bulgaria in scale 1:50 000 (Yordanov et al., 2008), it is observed that the fault structures usually follow the lithological contacts between the effusive and subvolcanic rocks from one side and the pyroclastic rock or sedimentary rocks from the other side. The pyroclastic rocks have some dubious properties concerning erosion susceptibility, which are expressed by the features listed below. The finer grained varieties usually have high percentage of volcanic glasses, which tend to alter after the deposition into clay minerals, thus clogging the water permeable paths. This greatly decreases the water permeability allowing this rock to act like an impermeable screen. On the other hand, the enrichment with

clay makes the rock soft, susceptible to mechanical erosion, and unable to support steep slopes. The nature of the volcanic activity in this region, however, has been dominated by predominantly acid and intermediate eruptions, which leads to the alternation of lava flows with high angle of repose and pyroclastics inverted to clayish rocks with low angle of repose. This is expressed by step-like natural slopes of the terrain, as usually the highest parts of the terrain are shielded by resistant rocks.

The variation in the erosional resistance of sedimentary rocks is also significant. Biohermal limestones typically form the upper parts of the terrain, while sandstones often occupy the lower areas. Alternations of sandstone and conglomerate show varying resistance to water erosion, depending on the degree of their lithification. In general, it can be assumed that Eocene sedimentary rocks tend to be more lithified than their Oligocene counterparts. However, original grain size and the chemical composition of the matrix also influence resistance. Coarser-grained rocks, such as conglomerates and breccias, are generally more resistant to erosion, and clastic rocks cemented with carbonate or chalcedony also exhibit high resistance.

The analysis of the rose-diagrams (Fig. 4) in relation to the geological structures and lithology in the respective zones (domains) shows the following:

Domain 1

The dominant stream orientation in this area is north–south (N–S), with a secondary east–west (E–W) trend (Fig. 4a). Several faults identified on the geological map trend northwest–southeast (NW–SE), and one fault is aligned approximately N–S. Bedding generally dips toward the southwest (SW). Given that the bedding dips SW while the primary stream orientation is N–S, it can be inferred that the drainage network is not structurally guided by bedding planes. This indicates that bedding is not the principal control on stream alignment. Although the main faults exhibit a NW–SE orientation, most streams do not follow these fault lines closely. This suggests that the development of the drainage network is largely independent of fault structures and is instead influenced by lithological factors that favour water erosion. Notably, some streams — particularly in the eastern and southwestern parts of Domain 1 — do exhibit alignment with mapped faults, implying localised structural control. In addition, vertical jointing or contrasts in lithology may also contribute to guiding stream paths in these areas. The most prominent example of tectonically controlled drainage is the channel occupied by the Byuyukdere River, which closely follows a structural lineament and reflects a stronger influence of faulting.

Domain 2

The dominant stream direction is clearly defined as E-W (Fig. 4b). Other directions appear almost symmetrically distributed around the centre of the diagram, suggesting lithological control, likely related to the sandy substrate. Bedding dips predominantly toward the southwest, although southeast and northward dips are also observed. Faults in domain 2 are sparse and mainly trend NW–SE or N–S; however, the E–W-oriented streams are not aligned with these faults. The area is primarily composed of sandstones, breccia-conglomerates, and tuffs. It can be assumed that stream orientation is more likely controlled by topographic slope or lithological variation, not by tectonic structures.

Fig. 4. Rose-diagram: a) Domain 1; b) Domain 2; c) Domain 3; d) Domain 5

Domain 3

Streams are clearly oriented along a N–S axis, with a secondary orientation trending NE–SW (Fig. 4c). The northern part of the domain is predominantly composed of sandstones

with some breccia-conglomerates, whereas the southern part is primarily built of tuffs. Faults are well developed, mainly trending NW–SE and nearly W–E. Bedding dips are variable, including NW, N, and some layers dipping NE. The main N–S drainage direction appears nearly orthogonal to the fault systems, suggesting that faults do not control stream orientation. The N–S erosional-drainage system through more complex lithology, is likely influenced by topography and difference in the erosion resistance of the rocks. It could be assumed that the NE–SW direction of the streams is controlled by small faults that are not visible at the mapping scale of the geological map used.

Domain 4

The dominant stream orientation is clearly NE–SW, with a secondary but less prominent trend along the N–S axis (Fig. 4d). Fault lines primarily trend NW–SE and do not align with the dominant stream direction. However, the main river — 4th and 5th order — flows from NNW to SSE, closely following the orientation of the same direction trending faults. These faults likely represent zones of structural weakness that have guided the river's course. It can be assumed that the younger valleys (1st and 2nd order streams) have developed independently of the fault systems, while the older, higher-order streams (4th and 5th order) are structurally controlled. The NE–SW stream alignment may be influenced by SW-dipping strata, local slope conditions, lithological variations, or by smaller faults conjugate to the NW–SE structures.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Byuyukdere watershed reveals a complex interaction between lithology, tectonic structures, and drainage development. While localised segments of the drainage system align with major faults, the overall stream orientations appear more strongly influenced by lithological contrasts and topographic gradients. The variability in erosional resistance among the volcanic and sedimentary rocks exerts a dominant control on drainage density and orientation.

Overall, the study shows that in moderately deformed terrains, drainage patterns are primarily controlled by lithology and slope, and less by tectonic structure. Integrating morphometric data with geological mapping improves understanding of basin evolution and supports erosion risk management in similar tectono-lithological settings. To sum up, the interplay between lithology and tectonics is essential for understanding the dynamics of erosion and the resultant drainage network development. Lithology provides the material context that influences erosion resistance, while tectonic activity controls the kinetics of landscape evolution. Together, these factors contribute to the complexity of geomorphological processes, underscoring the necessity for integrated analyses in future research.

Acknowledgements

Project: Debris Flows: Mechanisms of Formation, Dynamics, and Risk Management – A Case Study from the Byuyukdere River Catchment, Eastern Rhodopes, Contract No GPF-255 – 01.04.2025, University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”.

References

- Bartley, R., Poesen, J., Wilkinson, S., & Vanmaercke, M. (2020). A review of the magnitude and response times for sediment yield reductions following the rehabilitation of gullied landscapes. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 45(13), 3250–3279. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4963>
- Beeson, H. & McCoy, S. (2020). Geomorphic signatures of the transient fluvial response to tilting. *Earth Surface Dynamics*, 8(1), 123–159. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esurf-8-123-2020>
- Delcaillau, B., Carozza, J. M. & Laville, E. (2006). Recent fold growth and drainage development: the Janauri and Chandigarh anticlines in the Siwalik foothills, Northwest India. *Geomorphology* 76: 241–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2005.11.005>
- FAO-UNESCO-ISRIC (1990). Soil Map of the World, Revised Legend with corrections, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, World Soil Resources Report No 60, Italy, p. 140.
- Gabet, E. (2019). Lithological and structural controls on river profiles and networks in the northern Sierra Nevada (California, USA). *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 132(3-4), 655–667. <https://doi.org/10.1130/b35128.1>
- Haag, M., Schoenbohm, L., Wolpert, J., Jess, S., Bierman, P., Corbett, L., Sommer, C. A. & Endrizzi, G. (2025). Rock strength controls erosion in tectonically dead landscapes. *Science Advances*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adr2610>
- McCarthy, J., Schoenbohm, L., Bierman, P., Rood, D., & Hidy, A. (2019). Late quaternary tectonics, incision, and landscape evolution of the Calchaquí river catchment, Eastern Cordillera, NW Argentina. *Journal of Geophysical Research Earth Surface*, 124(8), 2265–2287. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019jf005091>
- Ramsey, L.A., Walker, R.T., Jackson, J., 2008. Fold evolution and drainage development in the Zagros Mountains of Fars province, south-east Iran. *Basin Res.* 20 (1), 23–48. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2117.2007.00342.x>
- Schumm, S.A. (1986). Alluvial river response to active tectonics. In: N.R. Council (Editor), *Active Tectonics*. National Academy Press, Washington (D.C.), pp. 80–94
- Seagren, E. and Schoenbohm, L. (2021). Drainage Reorganisation Across the Puna Plateau Margin (NW Argentina): Implications for the Preservation of Orogenic Plateaus. *Journal of Geophysical Research Earth Surface*, 126(8). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021jf006147>
- Strahler, A. N. (1957). Quantitative analysis of watershed geomorphology. *Trans. Am. Geophys. Union*, 38, 913–920; <https://doi.org/10.1029/TR038i006p00913>
- Twidale, C.R. (2004) River Patterns and Their Meaning. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 67, 159–218. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2004.03.001>
- Yanites, B., Becker, J., Madritsch, H., Schnellmann, M., & Ehlers, T. (2017). Lithologic effects on landscape response to base level changes: a modeling study in the context of the eastern Jura mountains, Switzerland. *Journal of Geophysical Research Earth Surface*, 122(11), 2196–2222. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016jf004101>
- Yordanov, B., Sarov, S., Georgiev, S., Dobrev, G., Moskovska, L., Grozdev, V., Balkanska, E. (2008). Geological map of the Republic of Bulgaria, Scale 1:50000, Map sheet K-35-75-G (Nikolovo). Ministry of Environment and Water, Bulgarian Geological Survey (In Bulgarian)